

Relationship between NIR and the Kjeldahl methods of measuring rice shoot N status.

yield can be increased by topdressing N when plant N is below 1.5% at panicle initiation.

A 2- to 3-d analysis service is planned. Farmers will collect samples of their crops, dry them in domestic microwave ovens, and send the dry samples to a central laboratory. The laboratory will complete the analysis and advise the farmer on the amount of N fertilizer needed. □

Effect of source and rate of phosphorus on yield and yield attributes of rice

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A field experiment was conducted during the wet season at the Crop Research Centre (29°N 79.3°E and 243.84 m altitude). The experimental field soil was Beni silty clay loam, fine-silty, mixed, hyperthermic, Aquic Hapludoll with pH 7.6, CEC 20 meq, 1.06% organic C, 20 kg available (Olsen) P/ha, and 196 kg available K/ha.

Five P sources—rock phosphate, single superphosphate, rock phosphate + superphosphate, rock phosphate + single superphosphate + pyrite, and

Grain yield and yield attributes of rice as influenced by source and rate of P. Nainital, India.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles/m ²	Filled grains/panicle	1000 grain wt (g)	Unfilled grain (%)
<i>Source</i>					
Rock phosphate	4.4	205	104	25.4	18.4
Superphosphate	5.4	252	108	25.7	13.1
Rock phosphate + superphosphate	4.7	219	107	25.8	15.7
Rock phosphate + superphosphate + pyrite	4.8	227	108	25.6	14.3
Rock phosphate + pyrite	4.7	220	108	25.8	15.2
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.2	7	2	ns	0.6
<i>Rate (kg P/ha)</i>					
13	4.6	215	106	25.5	17.1
26	4.8	228	107	25.8	14.9
40	4.9	231	108	25.7	14.0
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.2	5	2	ns	0.5
Control	4.3	193	100	25.6	20.4
Mean	4.77	223	107	25.6	15.6

rock phosphate + pyrite—at 3 rates—13, 26, and 40 kg P/ha—in 16 combinations were compared. Mussoorie rock phosphate : pyrite and single superphosphate : Mussoorie rock phosphate were mixed in 1:3 ratio. Mussoorie rock phosphate (100 mesh) was applied on the basis of 7% total P (2% citrate soluble). Pyrite was mixed and applied 15 d before transplanting in dry soil.

Rice variety Pant Dhan 4 seedlings were transplanted at 20- × 20-cm spacing at 2-3 seedlings/hill. The crop was fertilized with 120 kg N and 9 kg

Zn/ha. No K was applied.

Grain yield, panicles/m², and filled grains/panicle with single superphosphate were significantly higher than with all other sources of P (see table). Other sources were also significantly superior to rock phosphate alone in effect on yield and yield attributes. Percentage unfilled grains decreased significantly with single superphosphate but was significantly higher with rock phosphate than with any other source.

P significantly increased grain yield, panicles/m², and filled grains/panicle. □

Effect of modified urea on rice yield

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We studied the effect of an experimental coating material on N fertilizer use efficiency under lowland conditions during 1987 wet season. The coating material is a nonhydrous free-flowing liquid with a mild characteristic odor. The active principles that exert a nitrification regulatory effect are terpenoids and flavonoids compounded with certain polysaccharides and aldehydes.

The soil is a Vertisol with pH 8.4, CEC 50 meq/ 100 g soil, 0.1% total N (modified Kjeldahl method), and 6 ppm available P (Olsen's method). The experimental field was fertilized with 17.5 kg P and 33 kg K/ha at final puddling and 58 kg N/ha per treatment.

N fertilizers used were prilled urea (PU), large granule urea (LGU), and urea supergranule (USG). One percent of the experimental material and 5% neem cake powder were used to coat the modified urea materials.

Coated PU, LGU, and USG (hand placed 7 d after transplanting [DT]) with or without the new coating increased grain yield significantly over PU applied as standard split (2/3 basal, 1/3 at panicle initiation) (see table).